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Reclaiming the Self: Dreams, Desires, Decisions in Kavita Kané's *Ahalya's Awakening*

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Abstract:

This Research paper deals with Ahalya's power to reclaim the self, ambitious woman who dares to ignore the societal norms with her choices. Androcentric perspective had dominated the mythological narrations, which had consistently shown women characters as an ideal or victim to society. Their voice and contribution remains unheard, their roles are restricted to be ideal, beautiful and docile women. Retellings in postmodern literature had given more power and space to minor characters. Kavita Kané in her book *Ahalya's Awakening* shows infidelity as Ahalya's choice. Destiny from princess to Rishika is decided by her courage, determination and faith. Her assertion for the self should be embraced by the modern women, they need not to fear from the society nothing remains with them except self-satisfaction. The study highlights struggle of a woman who dared to dream, fulfils her desires by taking decisions for herself by ignoring the patriarchal norms.

Keywords: Ambitious, Dreams, Decisions, Desires, Rishika, Self-Satisfaction.

Introduction

India is one of the oldest civilization with history, culture, literature, heritage and intellectual wealth. The *Vedas*, *Puranas*, *Upanishads*, *Ramayana* and *Mahabharat* had given enormous

knowledge to the whole world. Mythology of every civilization showcase the wide images of its cultural and historical roots, stories of heroic deeds with unblemished values. Transmitted orally or in writing from generation to generation gets interpreted in multiple languages. Retellings in the field of mythology should be done by every generation so that we do not lose it. Kavita Kané, in her interview has emphasised on the importance of retellings of epics she says: “If the Indian epics *Ramyaana* and *Mahabharat* had not been re-imagined and retold multiple times, they wouldn't have existed today.” (Kané) Epics are relevant in society and characters are worshipped in divine form or questioned for their actions. Glorification of heroic actions and deeds, idealising them as giant figure is very common, but heroines in stories are seen as docile, beautiful who lack intellectual mind. Historical narration always lacked in feminist version of story; where every narration were dominated by the male hegemony. “Re-vision- the act of looking back, of seeing with fresh eyes, of entering an old text from a new critical section- is for us more than a chapter in cultural history: it is an act of survival.” (Rich 18) Retellings in 21st century had given more space to female characters, where their version of the story and role they played is read with utmost seriousness. In Indian English literature retellings have become trend, there are many writers who had re-imagined, re-visited, re-vised epics, where characters are not seen has divine form, instead they are seen as a human, who are to be judged and critically analysed for their actions. Writers like Amish Tripathi, Ashok Banker, Ashwin Shanghai, Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni, Devdutt Patnaik and many more had revisited epics with different lenses. Kavita Kané is a Pune-based Indian novelist who is well known for her books on minor characters from the Indian epics. Her major novels are *Karna's wife: The Outcast's Queen* (2014), *Sita's Sister* (2014), *Menaka's Choice* (2015), *Lanka's Princess* (2016), *Ahalya's Awakening* (2019). In the interview given to *The New Indian Express*, author had marked “We often view Mythology through the men's point of view, rarely the women's once the spotlight falls on these minor characters, we see them as independent

individuals who have their own story to tell, hidden in the larger narrative” (Kané). Her work majorly deals with marginalized and neglected characters from the new perspective, who suffered pain and suffering which had gone unheard in the earlier version of the epics because they were cleverly sidelined by the male writers. She had presented her characters bold, courageous, blunt, assertive, intelligent and witty. Every character is capable in the turning table in their favour.

Ahalya's Awakening is a retelling from the feminist perspective, where protagonist is at the centre of story. Ahalya one of the *Panchkanya* (“five maidens”) one of the most beautiful creation of Lord Brahma, Princess of Panchal and the daughter of King Mudgal was interested in education instead of marriage she wants to be Rishika. She was woman of substance who married men of her choice, became Rishika and reached ultimate goal of the life that is self-satisfaction. Her struggle still resonates with every women in the society who are always judged, only resilience of their own will lead towards self-realisation.

The purpose of the study is to analyse the character of protagonist in the context of agency to reclaim the self in Kavita Kané’s novel *Ahalya's Awakening*. Aim is to analyse the hurdles faced by Ahalya. Can a woman achieve self-satisfaction? Will she reclaim the herself? Kané has tried to put Ahalya’s version of the story, where she is the whole sole authority of her body, desires and decisions.

Ambitious Women

In Ancient India there were many female intellectuals, expert in their respective fields like Gargi, Maitreyi, Apala and Lopamudra. They had achieved remarkable heights in their educational field and became role models for the future generation. Education is the medium to release oneself from the domination of others, which leads towards empowerment and self-reliance. Woman education is the key issues of all the time, it is an assurances of freedom to

take decisions, which shows path towards enlightenment. Ahalya daughter of the intellectual father King Mudgal, who cannot be satisfied at ordinary things is stubborn to achieve her goal. Ahalya is a brilliant girl who wants to achieve the success through her higher education, and set a mark in the society, she doesn't appreciate role of the cloistered princes who does nothing, just possess luxurious life. Dignity and respect matters for every women society accepts individuals only on their achievement. Ahalya dreams to receive the higher education, being a book-lover, she wants to learn and gain knowledge, become self-reliant who cherish life with dignity. As every girl, Ahalya was been discouraged by her mother for higher education "You know you are very beautiful" (Kané 20). Queen Nalayani is obsessed by her daughter's beauty rather than intelligence, wanted her to marry the powerful man and bring fame to the family. Daughters are always considered suitable only for marriage, their dignity and self-worth do not count. As a mother it's matter of concern for her that Ahalya does not show interest in marriage nor being the beautiful matters, she takes it just as a god gift nothing related to individual achievement. Nalayani wanted her to carry the family legacy to get engaged with powerful and suitable suitor. "I am proud of my family, but that legacy, again, has been bestowed on me. It is a privilege, not a consequence of my personal abilities" (Kané 21). Lavishness of the royal family, living with privilege does not impress Ahalya, rather focus more on the personal achievements. Woman with intelligence and curiosity, wants to be recognized by the hard-work, hereditary achievement does not make sense to her. Ahalya's dream to become Rishika was considered ambitious she counters it with the question "Is it the right of just kings to be ambitious?" (Kané 64) dreams and aims of female are always questioned or marked irrelevant, society allows only man to be dreamer and ambitious. Intellectual ability of women are always seen with disbelief; they considered suitable only to the nourish a child which is the ultimate role they can play. Ahalya being ambitious women, rejects marriage proposal from the Lord Indra, and focuses on her dream to become Rishika.

Ahalya marries to Rishi Gautama which was against her mother wishes, for her being in love with him means to cherish the whole world. Married man of her own choice, enjoyed married life, became mother to three children, but slowly their marriage got stuck in dispute, and loneliness, which grabbed her mind and lead to desire for the physical intimacy with Lord Indra. Guilty of infidelity, tagged as a cheater, left alone by her children and husband pressurized her to seek salvation because she does not require anyone's sanction in her life, nobody is going to decide what her choices are going to be, no validation from anyone. Stands firmly embraces her desire for love "I searched all these years for myself and I only found Ahalya, the woman I was supposed to be born as: unblemished, without any faults, I had no Hala in me, no sin, no crime, no guilt" (Kané 345) Woman who agrees with her mistake, and accepts it whole heartedly. In world's eye she has turned into stone by Rishi Gautam, but in reality, it was her choice to remain away from the society's judgement, which lead her into deep meditation for many years, searching for her inner-self was the prime motive. She find true meaning of her name, accepted the fate, want to live without guilt and burden of sin by forgiving everyone. The renowned feminist, in her book, *Outlaw Culture: Resisting Representations*, suggest that: "The moment we choose to love we begin to move against oppression. The moment we choose to love we begin to move towards freedom, to act in ways that liberate ourselves and others." (Hooks 298). Loving oneself is a path which lead towards freedom, without worrying of any acceptance from anyone by enjoying her own solitude. Being true to oneself had no regret, and worry just living happy and content from within, accepting her desires no grudge against Lord Indra was gracefully embraced by Ahalya. "I lived the life given to me as a woman with all honesty, true to my instincts and faithful to my impulses, eager and yearning, but always true to myself. Always." (Kané 349) Being brutal honesty towards oneself is most precious gift one can give to her own-self. Ahalya was content with herself, happily enjoying her own company. Lived a life which was true to herself, became Rishika

highly learned woman, fulfilled her desire did not allow men to decide her future destiny. Transgression was her choice, with no sorrow, no regret, only satisfaction with solitude leading towards self-discovery. Ambition to gain supreme knowledge uplifted her from the societal norms and held her head high to celebrated individuality.

Re-interpretation of Ahalya

Revision of the classical text from feminist perspective is an attempt to rejuvenate mythology. Feminist writers believe male narration had portrayed women characters as minor and weak, failed to understand their psychology. Domination of patriarchy in literature texts exists in every civilization, narration of the stories became weapon to flourish the hegemony. Indian mythology is highly misogynistic where violence against women are celebrated. Androcentric narrations had devoiced many major characters who are holding more charm, fascination than the heroes of epic. Looking back to the classical texts with fresh perspective, giving more space to powerful minor characters by celebrating their individuality, assertiveness and bluntness. "Since the core of revisionist mythmaking for women poets lies in the challenge to and correction of gender stereotypes embodied in myth, revisionism in its simplest form consists of hit-and-run attacks on familiar images and the social and literary conventions supporting them" (Ostriker 73). There is a need to change the perspective, re-writing and re-vising mythology has set a trend which is encountering the mythical gender stereotypes. Feminist version of the stories allows to see the same saga from the different lens, which is an attempt to fill the gap in the societal conscious. Historical figures biasness are to be called out, reimagining will be helpful for the society to seek the example from the multiple version of the same myth.

Ahalya is the renowned figure gets mentioned in many texts like Shri Ramcharitmanas by Goswami Tulsidas and Adhyatma Ramayana where she is shown as minor character who

gets salvation by the mere touch of Shri Ram holy feet, praising him by singing glory to his name and family in return supreme lord bless her with boon and she returns back to her husband Rishi Gautam. Literary texts had shown women are submissive and guilty for their desires and ultimate aim is to return to their husband abode. Ahalya Re-interpretation had shown assertion of the female agency who do not bows down to the patriarchal norms, instead choose self and carries her own identity. Being in love with Rishi Gautam and getting married against the wishes of a family was not appreciated in society. It is a dream coming true, getting married to Rishi will support her to become Rishika and simultaneously will lead to happy married life. Gautam was a liberal sole who believed in equality of law for both the gender, was thoroughly working on women centric laws. Kané has shown different ideology of males one deals with Indra who is cruel and ungracious towards female, considers them as an object who should be possessed with domination and other is Rishi Gauatam who do not consider female as trophy who should be triumphed.

Ahalya gets occupied with household chores, ashram management and fostering her children, but there was no tracks which will leads towards her aim. Married life had trapped her, lacked mutual understanding with Rishi Gautam which developed rift in the relationship. Indra grasped that as an opportunity to seduce protagonist which is narrated has trap in multiple version of the story where Ahalya is victim of the plot, but in *Ahalya's Awakening* Kané has shown Ahalya's willingness in the situation to get intimate with Indra, but there also she desired only for Gautam's love "Yes, I knew he was not you,' she affirmed" (Kané 318). Ahalya accepts her action of intimation which was very personal feeling, every soul is free to choose partner, but that right was not cherished by second gender in patriarchal domination. Disobeyed law of the society, and priorities her right of desire "I had my reason to do what I did but will you anyone understand?" (Kané 321). She reclaimed herself, made Rishi Gautam's ignorance accountable for it, dared to accept her desire which allowed her to cross the boundary. Cursed

for the desire, turned into a stone, will get salvation by the mere feet touch of Lord Ram is the famous version of the story because its androcentric narration who subjugates woman.

Kané sees curse as a meditation to stay away from biased society. It is a choice to remain with yourself, which does not requires sanction from anyone, only a solitude filled with a blessing. Re-interpretation had given new perspective to Ahalya's curse, which holds selfishness towards oneself, does not require support from children and family members or any fellow beings. "It was my decision. You may call it a mistake, but it was my mistake and I was ready to suffer the consequence and obtain my redemption myself. No one else. Just like my happiness or unhappiness need not depend on any man or anyone else. Both come from within: the joy and the sadness." (Kané 345) Nor aspires for a position to hide from judgement, infidelity was a choice which she made, rather than a trap, does not seek any validation for her decision. It is a new version of minor character who upholds her agency to reclaim herself, who was earlier recognized as weak and submissive, but turns to be strong and woman of substance.

Self-Realisation

Purpose of the life which leads towards meaningfulness for every human being whether it is a male or female is the self-realisation. Ahalya dreamed to be Rishika kingdom, luxury, and wealth does not attract her, instead aims to pursue the higher education gets more firm. Falling in love and getting married to Rishi Gautam has indulge her into the domestic life, where she remained unworthy, even forgets her aim and individuality. Ahalya's infidelity was her decision Rishi Gautam cursed her and she was converted it into blessing. In the worlds eye she was cursed, Rishi Gautam has left the ashram, children disliked her with no further connect, she made herself invisible to the world. Meditation helped her to revisit the past which were filled with happiness because was she adored by everyone in the family, but discouraged for the higher studies, marrying Rishi Gautam, nourishing children and at last longing for the desire

of physical love has destroyed her whole life. Eventually she realized two men Indra and Rishi Gautam had destroyed her, Indra lusted for the bodily pleasure showed fake love and left her behind when caught. Rishi Gautam the man of logic in society's eye but in personal life he holds patriarchal attitude and lefts her after infidelity. Nobody questioned her curse; does it justify her decisions or its way society wants woman, who choose infidelity should be punished.

Silence in her life was not peace, somewhat inner turmoil and quest for new direction. She was far away from the societal judgement and harsh words; her new identity was dishonesty woman. Her Conversation with Sita show her knowledge of enlightenment, Ahalya discourage to identify women as daughter, wife and mother, instead advocates they belong to the larger world. "Wars make men into victors and even the vanquished are winners in their heroic deaths, But the women: they are always the victims" (Kané 343). Women is synonym of victimhood to draw separate image is very difficult, man save their manhood in the name of war and mission. They never fought for any land or luxury, instead it was addiction towards female body in the name of honour. Society enjoys women subjugation and the moral trial where they are the sole authority to decide punishment.

Ahalya does not wait for Ram to pardoned her, instead she choose Ram as a last person who recognized her plight without any biasness "I promised myself that I would wake up from my meditation and show myself to the world only in the presence of a just, enlightened soul. Ram was" (Kané 345). Society does not accept female assertion instead accepts narration which shows women as prey and needs a male shadow to be recognised in society. "I do not wish women to have power over men; but over themselves" (Wollstonecraft 69). Protagonist accepts her mistake without any doubt nor seek refuge for it "It was my decision. You may call it a mistake, but it was my mistake and I was ready to suffer the consequence and obtain my

redemption myself. No one else. Just like my happiness or unhappiness need not depend on any man or anyone else.” (Kané 345) Ahalya realized her worth which categorically depends on herself, instead seeking it outside she should search for it from the inner self.

Self-realisation is a salvation from all the worldly pleasure, and worries which release person from revenge, love, guilt and acceptance. The Universe had made you so powerful that you do not need any validation from anyone. Societal bias judgement cannot shake your confidence nor define your relevance. Ahalya reached that point in her life for which she always aspired, and she changed curse into blessing. Struggled to define herself, obeyed and rebelled in society, but at last found herself without any guilt. She lived a life true to herself without any remorse, meditation was not escape rather a path to seek herself and she was happy to find herself without any remorse, Gautam words comes true:

“The greatest of rishis and philosophers have lived their lives searching for this truth. About oneself in this life. It is about you, yourself, Ahalya. Just you.” (Kané 349)

Conclusion

Revision of mythology had given voice to voiceless, and marginalized characters. It is an attempt to show story from different point of view where domination of patriarchy in society has subverted second gender. The novelist is successful in putting out the story which resonates to every Indian women who have struggled, obeyed and rebelled every day in their respective life. Ahalya being brave woman had shown strength and honesty towards oneself. Societal pressure, judgement will never define your worth, instead your accountability towards oneself. Women are capable to live a life on their terms, does not seek any validation from men in public or personal life. Ahalya is an ambitious woman who dreamed to be learned woman with desires and right to take decisions. Her revised story is new way to reclaim the lost narrative and myth

who holds significance for the future. Self- Satisfaction is the ultimate goal of life, and recognition in one's own eye only matters at last.

Works Cited:

Anil Srinivasan. "Epics Would be lost if not Retold: Kavita Kane." *The New Indian Express*, 3 Sept 2018, www.newindianexpress.com/cities/chennai/2018/Sep/03/epics-would-be-lost-if-not-retold-kavita-kane-1866758.html. Accessed 29/06/2024

Rich, Adrienne. *When we Dead Awaken: Writing as Re-Vision. National council of Teachers of English, 1972.*

<https://opencourses.uoa.gr/modules/document/file.php/ENL9/Instructional%20Package/Texts//Readings/Feminism-20%Further%20Reading/RichAdrienne%20When%20We%20Dead%20Awaken-Writing%20as%20Re-vision.pdf>. Accessed 29/06/2025.

Kane, Kavita. "Demystifying Ahalya." *The New Indian Express*, 6 November 2019, <https://www.newindianexpress.com/cites/bengaluru/2019/Nov/06/demystifying-ahalya-2057525.html> Accessed 30/06/25

Kané, Kavita. *Ahalya's Awakening*. Rupa Publication, 2022.

Hooks, Bell. *Outlaw Culture: Resisting Representations*. Routledge, 2006.

Ostriker, Alice. *The Thieves of Language: Women poets and Revisionist Mythmaking*.

Chicago Journal, vol. 8, no. 1, 1982. 68-90,

<http://www.jstor.org/stable/3173482?origin=JSTOR-pdf>.

Wollstonecraft, Mary. *A Vindication of the Rights of Woman*. J. Johnson. 1792.